

Modeling and Parameter Optimization for a Variable Stiffness Mechanism employed in a Prosthetic Wrist

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Abstract—Variable Stiffness Actuators (VSAs) feature nonlinear output torque and stiffness functions, which can be difficult to derive and analyze. Therefore, sizing VSAs to fit a specific application may be a challenging task.

In this work, we provide some guidelines to model VSAs, deriving their output torque and stiffness functions and choosing the elastic parameters to obtain a desired behavior, applying the methodology to a mechanism employed in a prosthetic wrist.

Index Terms—Robotics, Variable Stiffness Actuators, Model, Parametric Variability

I. INTRODUCTION

In the latest years, Variable Stiffness Actuators (VSAs) found space in many different applications, thus withstanding distinct requirements [1]. However, designing VSAs to suit a specific application is not trivial due to the peculiar nonlinearity of the system, which is required to modulate the impedance of the joint [2].

In this work, we present the procedure we applied to derive the torque and stiffness functions of the VSA employed in [3] to craft a 3 DoF prosthetic wrist. Moreover, Section III reports a study on the parametric variation that we exploited to choose the elastic parameters that satisfy the system requirements. Precisely, the actuation system is sized to manipulate a maximum load of 1.2 kg and match the stiffness range of the human wrist. A lower bound for its stiffness is found in [4].

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The nonlinear elastic transmission adopted in [3] is shown in Figure 1. It employs an antagonistic setup of linear springs, tendons, and pulleys to achieve nonlinearity thanks to the geometry of the arrangement. The linear springs modulate the

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Fig. 1. Scheme of one branch of the nonlinear elastic transmission mechanism and definition of the geometric parameters needed to derive (3).

tension on the tendons through a lever arm mechanism, thus regulating the output stiffness and torque.

Focusing on one branch at a time, we derive an analytical function of the output torque using the lever angle γ and the deflection between output and motor pulleys δ . Therefore, the elastic energy of one branch is

$$U_s(\gamma) = \frac{1}{2}k(L(\gamma) - L_0)^2, \quad (1)$$

where $L(\gamma) = \sqrt{(l_n \sin(\gamma) + d_0)^2 + (l_n(1 - \cos(\gamma)))^2}$ is the spring length, L_0 is its free length, k is its elastic constant, d_0 is its length computed for $\gamma = 0$, and l_n is the length of the horizontal lever arm. Differentiating (1) to obtain the actuated torque

$$\tau(\gamma) = -\frac{\partial U_s}{\partial \delta} = -\frac{\partial U_s}{\partial \gamma} \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \delta} = -\frac{\partial U_s}{\partial \gamma} \left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial \gamma} \right)^{-1}. \quad (2)$$

The relationship $\delta(\gamma, L_t)$ can be found from the geometry of the actuation system by imposing the conservation of the tendon length L_t as in [3], obtaining

$$L_t = R_p \beta_m + BC + r_G \beta_G + DE + R_p \beta_p = f(\delta, \gamma). \quad (3)$$

Therefore, measuring δ with rotational encoders and assuming L_t known by design, it is possible to compute γ , thus the actuated torque. Differentiating the output torque yields the stiffness of the joint σ as

$$\sigma(\gamma) = -\frac{\partial \tau_{joint}}{\partial \delta} = -\frac{\partial \tau_{joint}}{\partial \gamma} \left(\frac{\partial \delta}{\partial \gamma} \right)^{-1}. \quad (4)$$

III. STUDY ON THE PARAMETRIC VARIATION

Once obtained the characteristics of the nonlinear spring, we studied the effect of each elastic parameter (i.e., L_t, d_0, k, L_0) on the shape of the output functions to choose the best values to fit the application.

The length of the tendons acts directly in (3), affecting the function $\gamma(\delta, L_t)$, and thus the permitted deflection range. The geometry of the nonlinear elastic system bounds the feasible range of L_t . If the cables are too short, the branches of the actuation system become parallel, and the tension of the cables tends to infinity. On the contrary, if the tendons are too long, they wouldn't remain tight to the lever pulley. An upper bound is found by imposing that the springs always work in extension, obtaining

$$\sqrt{(l_n \sin(\gamma) + d_0)^2 + (l_n(1 - \cos(\gamma)))^2} \geq L_0. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2a shows that longer transmission cables reduce output stiffness and that the system is highly sensible to a variation of this parameter.

Changing the distance of the spring anchor points d_0 or its free length L_0 varies the spring preload and, thus, the stiffness of the joint. Precisely, by increasing d_0 or decreasing L_0 , the output stiffness and torque grow (see Fig. 2b). These parameters also act on (5), so they should be carefully selected to avoid the detachment of the tendons.

The elastic constant of the springs k influences the output torque and stiffness. As shown in Fig. 2d, stiffer springs yield higher output torque and stiffness with lower deformation.

IV. DISCUSSION

Each elastic parameter acts directly on some features of the output function. However, their combination should be chosen considering the maximum torque τ_{max} deliverable by the actuators. For example, if k is too high, the torque limit is reached at low deflection, meaning that the actuation system is not exploiting the most sloped (i.e., highest stiffness) part of the characteristics typical of high deflections. As a consequence, the maximum output stiffness is reduced. Using softer springs, it is possible to fully exploit the δ operational range given by the geometry of the elastic system, which provides higher stiffness at its extreme. However, if the springs are too soft, the actuator must be in a rigid configuration to compensate for even moderate load, losing controllability of the stiffness.

Therefore, the elastic parameters employed in [3] are chosen considering this trade-off, the availability of the technology, and the resulting range of stiffness, finally obtaining the performance reported in Fig. 3d.

Fig. 2. Output torque on varying elastic parameters. The quantities with the superscript n are the nominal values employed for the prototype in [3]. Each subfigure reports the variation of a single parameter: (a) tendon length L_t ($\Delta = 0.5$ mm), (b) spring free length L_0 (or anchor points distance d_0), (c) spring rate k . Panel (d) shows the compliance ellipsoid of the prosthetic wrist obtained with such parameters at 0, 10, 33, and 100 percent of the maximum motor torque (respectively $C_0, C_{10}, C_{33}, C_{100}$), comparing them with the lower bound C_0^H given by [4] for the human wrist in passive configuration.

V. CONCLUSION

This work provides some guidelines to model VSAs, derive their torque function, and size the actuation system for a specific application, applying the proposed methodology to the mechanism employed in [3] for a prosthetic wrist. Nonetheless, this procedure could be extended to actuators with different geometries. The real behavior of the actuator should, of course, be confirmed by experimental data since non-ideal phenomena such as hysteresis and friction are not taken into consideration in this analysis. However, the obtained function should be suitable to fit the experimental behavior of the system.

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